

USING GAMES TO TEACH YOUNG CHILDREN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Abdullahayeva Mohina Sobitxon qizi

Toshkent viloyati, Chirchiq davlat pedagogika instituti

Turizm fakulteti Xorijiy til va adabiyoti 21/4 guruh talabasi

Abstract: The author of the article discusses the game as a method of teaching English lessons in primary classes. As a result, the author concludes that the game has a universality that allows you to adapt it to different goals and tasks. Game techniques perform many functions in the process of child development, facilitate the learning process, help to learn the increasing material every year and unobtrusively develop the necessary competencies.

Keywords: didactic, students, games, active, interesting, help, develop

We all know that in primary classes, the foundations of knowledge, skills and practical skills that are necessary for further education are laid. Moral qualities are formed, children's ability to master knowledge independently, and their interest in learning and creative search is aroused.

In my opinion, one of the most effective ways to develop an interest in the subject, along with other methods and techniques that are used in the classroom, is the game. Even K.D.Ushinsky advised to include game moments in the serious work of students so that the process of learning was more productive.

I believe that with the help of the game, interest in foreign languages develops and the first encounter with the foreign world of another country occurs. It's no secret that the game makes it even easier to focus students' attention and engage them in active work. All this is due to the psychological characteristics of the child's body. The game makes it possible to make the process of repeating the vocabulary and grammatical structures fun for students. The use of educational games makes it possible to think actively, developing creative abilities while completing tasks, to develop the abilities inherent in the child's nature. There are a huge number of games that will help any

English teacher diversify their lesson and make it more interesting. I want to present some of them that I have been using in my lessons for years. By naming letters of the alphabet from A to Z, students add a phrase with a word to their letter: “A is for Apple”, “B is for Ball”.

I propose to decipher a phrase in which each letter is encoded by a number that corresponds to the ordinal number of letters in the alphabet: A-1, B-2, C-3. (9), (12,9,11,5), (5,14,7, 12, 9, 19, 8)- I like English. Two students from different teams come to the Board. They must remember three words that start with a given letter and write them on the Board. Then the children read the written words. For each correctly written and read the word, the team receives a point. Students are asked to find words in sentences where the same letter is read differently. The one who completes the task faster and more correctly gets a point.

One of the best moments in the game is when the child gets a surprise. What if it's a surprise assignment? Recently, I quite often began to use in my practice kinder — surprises, or rather eggs from kinder. Inside the eggs, you can hide any word or sentence that needs to be translated. You can also hide grammar tasks. Any child will be happy to take a surprise and look at what is in it, trying to cope with the task. In another interesting game, I involve children in the process of learning words with the help of a game with flyswatters. In advance on the Board, I write the words in a different order from the required topic. I call two students to the blackboard and give them flyswatters. The point of the game is that when the teacher calls a word, students must quickly find it on the Board and slap it. The winner is the one who slapped the most words (if the words on the Board are written in Uzbek, the teacher pronounces them in English and Vice versa).

Of course, you cannot do without more standard, but no less interesting games with cards. For example, the game “Calendar”. The teacher in the classroom puts up numbers from one to seven, which indicate the ordinal number of the day of the week. Seven students receive cards with the days of the week written on them. Students' task: stand in front of the number that defines the day of the week. Each child names the day of the week on their cards. Students are offered an unfamiliar image on the topic

“Appearance”, such as a portrait of a boy. The children take turns describing his features, clothing, and character. Everyone has the right to say only one sentence. The task will be more exciting if the teacher takes a portrait of a famous person.

In my classes, children often ask for a “Step by step” game. This game is for checking new words. Students should stand away from the teacher. Then the teacher sets a word (for example Board games). The one who first correctly translates board games will take a step towards the teacher if the student does not know the word, he stands still. The winner is the one who reaches the teacher faster.

I can't help but think of the game “Snowball”, which I use both in the Junior and middle levels. One student utters the phrase: I see a pen. The next student repeats this phrase and adds another word: I see a pen and a textbook. The winner is the one who names the most items in the order in which the children named them. And you can also conduct this game with the help of images.

During games, we must remember that the game should make children think and be active. Waiting a long time for your turn to be included in the game reduces interest in it. The material that is used during the game should be easy to use. If several games are played in a lesson, we should alternate between light and heavy games.

Game “The last letter.” Two teams are formed. The representative of the first team calls the word, students from the second team must come up with a word with the letter that ends the word named by the first team, and so on. The winner is the team that last called the word.

For example tea, apple, egg, etc.

The game “What's in the box?”. One of the students draws a gift box on the blackboard, tells who the gift is for, and asks the others to guess what's in it. If it is difficult for children to guess, the theme of the gift is indicated, for example, “Food”, “Clothing”. This game allows you to repeat all the vocabulary for a year of training. It can also be timed to coincide with the birthday of one of the students.

“Bingo” game. Pre-prepared cards for each student with words on a specific topic, or students themselves in a notebook write down 5-6 words from the topic being

studied. The teacher calls the words on the topic, the named word must be crossed out. The one who first crosses out all the words shouts “Bingo!” and becomes the winner.

Game “Guess the riddles”. Students are divided into two teams. The teacher gives riddles to each team in turn. For example: “It is a vegetable. It is long. It is orange» (Carrot). The team that has guessed the most riddles wins.

The game is "Colours". The task is to name items of the same colour. The team that can name more items and animals of the same colour wins.

The game is "More – less”. Learn the phrases: It is more. It is less. That's it. The driver thinks of a number. The others ask questions, trying to guess. The one who guessed the number becomes the driver of the game.

Is it seven? - It is more.

Is it ten? — It is less.

Is it nine? — It is less.

Is it eight? — That's it.

“Name the word” game. Game progress: The teacher takes turns throwing the ball to the participants of the game, calling the sound. Participants return the ball by naming the word in which this sound is heard (based on the studied vocabulary).

Game “What sound do I have in mind?” The teacher names a string of words that contain the same sound, and the other participants in the game guess this sound. This game helps you form your listening skills from the first lessons.

Game “Unusual phone”. Game progress: A large phone is drawn on the Board with transcription characters instead of numbers. All participants of the game are divided into two teams. The task of the teams is to type familiar words that the teacher pronounces by sounds.

Summing up, we can say that the game is a traditional, recognized method of training and education. This is a unique tool for non-violent education of children.

The game meets the natural needs and desires of the child, and therefore with its help, he will learn with pleasure. Play is an activity in which the child first emotionally and then intellectually learns the entire system of human relations. They have a

complex effect on the intellectual, emotional, volitional, communicative and other aspects of the growing personality.

References

1. Shaykhislamov, N. (2020). Cognitive Linguistics, the Symbolic and Interactive Functions of Language. *Образование и наука в XXI веке, 1(6)*, 390-393.
2. Shaykhislamov, N. (2020). Linguistic and Cultural Aspects of Bread Baking Terms in English and Uzbek Languages. *Фан ва таълим интеграцияси: имконият ва тенденциялар, 62-64*.
3. Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Ona tili fanini o‘qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish. *O‘zbekistonda ilm-fan va ta’lim masalalari: muammo va yechimlar, (3)*, 71-73.
4. Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Nutqning paralingvistik va ekstralingvistik vositalari. *Ўзбекистонда илмий-амалий тадқиқотлар, 36-37*.
5. Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Gender tilshunosligining fundamental nazariy asoslari va gender masalalari. *XXI asr tilişunosligi va tarjimaşunosligining dolzarb muammolari: nazariya, amaliёт, innovatsiya, 144-146*.
6. Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Ona tili darslarida interfaol usullardan foydalanish. *Prospects of Development of Science and Education, 1(2)*, 247-249.
7. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Ўзбек ва рус тилларида қўлланилувчи инвестиция ва кредит терминларининг қиёсий типологик таҳлили. *Филологиянинг умумназарий масалалари, 204-206*.
8. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Студенттердің ана тілі мен әдебиеті пәнін меңгерудің педагогикалық негіздері. *Образование и наука в XXI веке, 1(6)*, 421-426.
9. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Зооним компонентли метафораларнинг антропоцентриқ тадқиқ этишда гендер жиҳатлар. *Образование и наука в XXI веке, 1(6)*, 304-309.

10. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Лингвомәдениеттанудың тарихи мен теориялық негіздері. *О‘zbekistonda ilm-fan va ta’lim masalalari: muammo va yechimlar*, (2), 219-221.
11. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Абай поэзиясындағы философиялық сарын. *Абай ижоди ва илмий меросини ўрганиши масалалари*, 154-157.
12. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Фондаментхон технологияи асосии забон ва назарияи гендерӣ. *Мактабгача таълим муассасаларида, умумтаълим мактабларида ва олий таълим муассасаларида чет тиллар ўқитишининг узвийлиги*, 734-735.
13. Шофқоров, А. М. (2018). Fonetik takrorlar va ularning uslubiy xususiyatlari. *Ta’lim tizimida ijtimoiy gumanitar fanlar*, (4), 79-86.
14. Шофқоров, А. М. (2019). Kelishik turlarini o‘rganishda interfaol ta’lim metodlaridan foydalanish. *Til va adabiyot masalalari*, (5), 18-19.
15. Шофқоров, А. М. (2020). Ҳамид Олимжон шеърлятида фонетик такрорлар. *Филологиянинг умумназарий масалалари*, 60-62.
16. Шофқоров, А. М., & Ходжамқулов, У. Н. (2019). “Vor”ning inkori va “Yo‘q”ning tasdig‘i haqida mulohazalar. *Til va adabiyot ta’limi*, (2), 25-26.
17. Shofqorov, A. M., & Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Ona tili ta’limda lingvistik mashqlarning o‘rni. *Science and Education*, 1(Special Issue 2).
18. Shayxislamov, N. Z., & Makhmudov, K. S. (2020). Linguistics and Its Modern Types. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 1(1), 358-361.
19. Shayxislamov, N. (2020). Ona tili fanini o‘qitishning muammolari. *Science and Education*, 1(Special Issue 2).
20. Shayxislamov, N. Z. Umumta’lim maktablarida ona tili fanini o‘qitishda sinfdan tashqari ishlarni tashkil etish. *Science and Education*, 1(7), 373-378.
21. Махмудов, Қ. Ш., Санакулов, З. И., Шайхисламов, Н. З., & Қаршиева, Д. Э. (2020). Педагогик таълимда "Кластер". *Science and Education*, 1(7), 587593.
22. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Ўқувчиларнинг нутқий компетенцияларни ривожлантиришда нутқнинг илмий-назарий изоҳи. *Science and Education*, 1(5).

23. Kizi, J. K. G., & Ugli, M. K. S. (2020). Teaching culture as a tool to English Teaching Methodology. *Science and Education*, 1(3).
24. Matkasimova, D. B. K., & Makhmudov, K. S. U. (2020). Importance of Interactive Methods in the English Language Grammar Teaching. *Science and Education*, 1(Special Issue 2).
25. Ugli, M. K. S., & Qizi, A. D. A. (2020). Raising English Learning Awareness of Students whose Specialties are Non-linguistic. *Science and Education*, 1(3).
26. Шайхисламов, Н. (2020). Изучение языка в социолингвистике и культура речи. *Экономика и социум*, 10(77).
27. Shayxislamov, N. Z. (2020). Lingvokulturologiyaning fanlar sistemasidagi maqomi va uning etnolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika va etnopsixolingvistika bilan bog'liqligi. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 1(2), 221-231.
28. Makhmudov, K. (2020). Innovative Cluster of Pedagogical Education: Common Goals and Specific Interests. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 1(2), 182-187.